

A NEW METHOD FOR THE PREPARATION OF SELENIUM DIOXYDIFLUORIDE, SeO_2F_2

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Selenium, unlike sulphur, yields only a few compounds in the highest state of oxidation. SeF_6 , unstable SeO_3 , and selenates, e.g., salts of SeO_4^{2-} , are the only few known compounds of hexavalent selenium. Recently fluoroselenates, e.g. salts of $\text{SeO}_3\text{F}^{2-}$, pentafluoroselenium hypofluorite, F_5SeOF , and *bis*-pentafluoroselenium peroxide, $\text{F}_5\text{SeO.OSeF}_5$, have been described (Mitra *et al.*, *Science & Culture*, 1955, 20, 351; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 2646).

Sulphuryl fluoride, SO_2F_2 , a stable compound of hexavalent sulphur, is known for a long time. The corresponding selenium compound, SeO_2F_2 , has recently been prepared by digesting one mole of BaSeO_4 with 14 moles of HSO_3F at 50° (Englebrecht and Stoll, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1957, 292, 20). Another method for the preparation of the same compound is by boiling SeO_3 with excess AsF_3 under reflux for many hours (Jerschkevitx, *Angew. Chem.*, 1957, 69, 562).

Selenium dioxydifluoride, SeO_2F_2 , was also prepared in this laboratory by fluorinating SeO_2 in AgF_2 - AgF catalytic chamber. The present note describes the method of preparation in details.

Procedure.—Powdered selenium dioxide was taken in a copper vessel (about 500 c.c.) fitted with an inlet and an outlet tube. The vessel was heated to about 200° . The vapour pressure of SeO_2 at this temperature is about 54 mm. Dry nitrogen gas was passed into the vessel and the outlet tube, which was of very short length, was directly connected to a big nickel tube of about a meter long and 5" in diameter.

This nickel tube, acting as a catalytic chamber, was filled with copper turnings, very finely plated with silver.*

The catalytic chamber was heated to about 100° and a large excess of fluorine, carried by nitrogen gas, was introduced inside through another inlet tube. After leaving the chamber the gas was passed through a glass trap, cooled externally by liquid oxygen. Fluorine was used in such excess that unchanged fluorine emerged from the condenser trap.

The product was found to be a mixture of (a) SeF_6 (excess), (b) SiF_4 (appreciable), (c) SeO_2F_2 (moderate), (d) SeOF_6 (?), and (e) a residue boiling above 0° , possibly containing various oxyfluorides such as SeOF_2 , $\text{Se}_2\text{O}_2\text{F}_{10}$, etc.

Separation of SeO_2F_2 .—The mixture taken in a pyrex tube was kept immersed in acetone and dry ice. SiF_4 and partly SeF_6 were thus removed. The mixture was then distilled under a little pressure with a fractionating column of about 4' height and packed with nickel balls. After removal of SeOF_6 and SeF_6 a compound was found to boil nearly at -10° at normal pressure.

The molecular weight was determined by vapour density method. The average experimental value found was 149.2 (the theoretical value is 148.9). The compound during second distillation was found to boil at about -9° .

This work was done in late 1955 and early 1956, at the Fluorine Chemistry Laboratory, University of Washington, Seattle, under the guidance of Prof. G. H. Cady, and supported by the office of Naval Research, U.S.A.

*For the detailed description of the Catalytic Chamber the original papers of Cady *et al.* should be consulted.